

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING MORAL AND ETHICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations and effectiveness of developing the moral and ethical competence of future pedagogues, the improved methodical foundations and technological system of developing the moral and ethical competence of future pedagogues. Also, the content of developing the spiritual and moral competence of future pedagogues was analyzed.

Key words: technology, competence, improvement, pedagogical, technological, model, didactic, spiritual-ethical competence, cognitive, active, result, form, method, tool, assessment, pedagogical experiment.

INTRODUCTION. Spiritual and moral competence as an integrative feature of a person combines spiritual knowledge, the ability to determine one's place in the system of spiritual values, and the ability to demonstrate spiritual maturity in a wide range of life situations. The main functions of this competence include: axiological, directive and management. The structure of the development of moral and ethical competence appropriately includes the following components: introductory-analytical, value-oriented, reflexive-active. These components also reflect the social description of spiritual-moral competence: information with spiritual content is analyzed and evaluated from the point of view of universal human values, creatively compatible with personal-spiritual values, to understand other people. It is necessary for it to be expressed in a convenient form, to be developed on the basis of evidence based on the consideration of different options of spiritual values, to make the right movement within the framework of moral reflection and wide life situations. In turn, these components serve as indicators of the development of spiritual and moral competence in students.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. G.V. Izbullayeva, M.E. Ismoilova, V. Karimova, U. Mahkamov, N. Dj. Mahmudova, B. Sh. Mirzaolimov, O.Musurmonova, S.Nishonova, Sh.SH.Olimov, N.Kh.Oripova, N.Ortikov, Sh.S.Shodmonova, Sh.Kurbanov, M.Kuronov, A.Haidarov, Sh.T.Halilov, J.Hasanboyev, O. Hasanboyeva; issues of spiritual, ethical and professional training of future specialists N.E. Azimova, M.E. Ahmedova, Z. Ismoilova, Sh.Q.

Mardonov, G.I. Mahmutova, N.M. Ochilova, Sh. Rayimov, B.Kh. Rahimov, Z.T. Saliyeva, O'.Q. Utanov, N.M. Egamberdiyeva conducted scientific research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In the research work of N.M. Ochilova, who studied the formation of pedagogic moral qualities in students as a separate object, the theoretical foundations and characteristics of the problem were analyzed and effective approaches used in this regard were presented. In the study, a model of the formation of pedagogic moral qualities was developed. In addition, the current state of moral upbringing of students, the manifestation of moral qualities necessary for pedagogical activity were studied in the work.

As a result of the research, it was found that students have a positive moral attitude towards pedagogical work and nature. In the course of the research, a special course called "Ethics of a teacher" was organized, in which "Society's attitude towards the teacher's personality", "Teacher's attitude towards society", "Attitude towards the motherland", "Self-attitude", "Attitude to work", "Attitude to people", lectures on the characteristics of pedagogic ethics, reflection of professional ethics qualities in relationships and its uniqueness, and practical trainings were organized based on interactive methods. In order to develop moral relations of students to the country where they were born and raised, a team called "Motherland" was formed, and the fact that their tasks in this regard were clearly indicated is of scientific and methodological importance.

B.H. Rahimov's dissertation on the issue of the formation system of professional-cultural relations in the future teacher analyzed professional-cultural relations from a socio-pedagogical point of view. "In the system of professional, cultural and professional-cultural relations, students' relations were studied in four directions. These are: the student's attitude towards himself, his peers, adults and the community. Based on the obtained results, the structure of the future teacher's professional and cultural relations was developed" shows the effectiveness of the research conducted in cooperative pedagogy.

In preparing students to study national-spiritual values, the researcher N.Kh. Kushvaktov stated that "the theoretical, pedagogical and psychological foundations of developing students' knowledge of national-spiritual values based on information technologies were determined, teaching students national-spiritual values based on information technologies that the content, methods and pedagogical conditions have been defined, that the ways of organizing the use of information technologies in the process of learning national-spiritual values have been clarified and that a suitable computer program has been

created, that national-spiritual values can be taught using information technologies that the level of effectiveness of the learning-oriented pedagogical process has been proven, that in the process of teaching national and spiritual values on the basis of information technology, a multi-stage and continuous informational communicative technology called "Values" has been developed, "Pedagogy", "History of Pedagogy" from this technology, the preparation of methodological recommendations for the use of subjects such as "Folk pedagogy" in the teaching of national and spiritual values based on information technology, and the development of tests and methodical manuals that make students more active in the process of teaching national-spiritual values based on information technology. inspires hope and confidence.

In the research work of O.R. Jamoliddinova on improving the pedagogical mechanisms of adherence to the principles of integrity and continuity in the development of the healthy culture of young people, a model of problem improvement was developed based on philosophical, psychological, legal, and social approaches, the development of a healthy culture of young people, a healthy life to understand and realize the need for forgiveness, to determine the indicators of its development, taking into account the observance of the culture of healthy living by oneself and those around him, to evaluate the content and effectiveness of social projects aimed at developing the culture of healthy living among young people in raising a mature generation " indicates that the concept of "family, neighborhood, school cooperation" is extremely important. The same problem in Z.T.Saliyeva's dissertation, as an example of improving the mechanisms of developing the spiritual culture of students of pedagogical higher education institutions, by clarifying its philosophical, pedagogical and psychological factors, the interpersonal, group, collective and value-oriented integrative effect of professional socialization. It is highlighted through the analysis of the display mechanism, the informational-cognitive, personal-value-oriented emotional-emotional, activity-creative components of diagnosing the level of development of spiritual culture in students, as well as the professional-pedagogical orientation of the diagnostic apparatus, evaluation of pedagogical communication skills, improved by determining the level of empathy and success, the development of spiritual culture is related to familiarity, knowledge; assessment, reflection, choice; interiorization; manifestation of qualities in activity; based on the integration of strengthening and correction stages, local-module technology has been developed, effective communication techniques have been formed in students, preparation for activities aimed at consciously

changing one's behavior, and management of thought processes based on the unity of external and internal influences. the improvement of neurolinguistic programming technologies for the development of spiritual culture, as well as the development of technology for ensuring information security in the conditions of man-made civilization and developing reading and reading culture determine the scientific and practical value of the work.

The scientific research carried out by N.M. Egamberdiyeva is characterized by the fact that it reflects a number of modern approaches to the development of the spiritual culture of students of higher educational institutions and moral education under the influence of the environment in vocational education. According to the scientist, the development of the spiritual culture of students in the higher education system should be built on the basis of a cultural-humanitarian approach. In contrast to these works, the research work of N.A. Muslimov is distinguished by the fact that it is aimed at the scientific and methodological analysis of the theoretical and methodological bases of the professional formation of the teacher of vocational education. In the dissertation, historical, logical, dialectical criteria are distinguished for determining methodological ideas and views in determining the path and direction of the teacher's professional formation. The personal and professional development of the teacher is considered as the process of realizing one's potential, and creativity is considered as an objective need to design one's professional activity.

The ideas of individual design of the teacher's professional training process are highlighted as an objective leading criterion of professional-pedagogical education.

The problem of development of historical thinking among students of general education schools by means of modernized didactic support was studied by B. Khodzhayev, and in the course of the research, work was carried out to improve the conceptual foundations of the issue and the practical-technological system.

In the methodical manual "Basics of spiritual and moral education" created by J. Hasanboyev, M. Turopova, O. Hasanboyeva, spiritual and moral education given to a child with the same problem in the family, general secondary education Forms and methods of organizing spiritual-educational and moral education in schools have been developed, pedagogical skills and its main principles have been defined, and the work plan of deputy directors for spiritual-educational education has been developed.

In the study of the problem of developing the spiritual and moral competence of the future teacher, we consider A.G. Asmolov that a person is a person, a being that actively reacts to the results of personal experience, potential motives, character, abilities, activities, including self-discovery. We relied on the theory that it is necessary to study as an improving subject choice. By determining the exact content of this idea, we tried to determine "the meaning that describes the existence of the studied phenomenon for the student."

Psychologist G.S. Abramova studied in detail the problems related to the spiritual self-realization of young people and identified the aspects that clearly testify to the fact that they are actively going through this process. First of all, this is spiritual empathy, that is, feeling in common with other people and being independent from them, to others (in rare cases, it can be indifferent), to oneself, to friendship (a teenager is a close confidant seeks), is related to the strength of the desire for love (given to man) and the relationship with the universe.

Another group of scientists, V.I. Slobodchikov and Y.I. Isayev, characterized the period of youth as a stage of individualization and paid attention to the fact that young people have a special attitude to morality. They considered the level of individualization as the main stages of human life related to the formation of a personal worldview, individual identity and uniqueness. "The main problem of young people is to find their individual, true personal relationship to social existence, subculture and time."

CONCLUSION. Therefore, the development of spiritual and moral competence as an integrative feature of a student includes spiritual and moral knowledge, the opportunity to determine one's place in the system of spiritual and moral values, and the manifestation of spiritual maturity in a wide range of life situations. combines the ability. These components also reflect the social description of spiritual-moral competence: information with spiritual content is analyzed and evaluated from the point of view of universal human values, creatively compatible with personal-spiritual values, to understand other people. it is necessary for it to be expressed in a convenient form, to be developed on the basis of evidence based on the consideration of different options of spiritual values, to make the right movement within the framework of moral reflection and wide life situations. In turn, these components serve as indicators of the development of spiritual skills in students.

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